

Application of the Red Relief Image Map (RRIM) in Geomorphological Analyses: Examples from Croatia

Marin Mićunović^{1,*}, Sanja Faivre¹

¹ University of Zagreb, Faculty of Science, Department of Geography, Zagreb, Croatia, mmicunov@geog.pmf.hr, sfaivre@geog.pmf.hr

* corresponding author

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20407465

Abstract: The development of LiDAR and digital elevation models has significantly improved the analysis of geomorphological forms, yet the interpretation of microrelief remains limited by standard DEM visualisations, particularly due to their dependence on illumination direction and weaker representation of concave–convex surface relationships. This study assesses the applicability of the Red Relief Image Map (RRIM) method for the interpretation of relief forms in three morphogenetically different relief types in Croatia: the tufa barriers of the Zrmanja River, the Kubarnovo brdo landslide in Hrvatska Kostajnica, and the glacial relief forms of Bilensko Mirovo. The analysis was based on a LiDAR-derived digital elevation model with a spatial resolution of 1×1 m. For each locality, hillshade, slope and RRIM visualisations were produced and compared using a qualitative comparative approach. The results show that RRIM provides the clearest representation of microrelief relationships at all analysed localities, although its advantages vary depending on geomorphological context. Overall, RRIM proved to be a valuable complementary tool for geomorphological interpretation and detailed mapping of subtle relief structures.

Keywords: RRIM; geomorphology; geomorphometry; visualisation.

1 Introduction

Geomorphological analyses are conducted at different spatial scales, from large morphostructural and macrorelief units to meso- and microrelief forms. Scale of analysis is therefore one of the key issues in geomorphology, since landforms cannot be equally successfully recognized and interpreted at all spatial levels. For this reason, geomorphometry developed as a discipline focused on the extraction and quantitative analysis of landforms and on understanding the processes that shaped them (Hengl and Reuter 2009). Today, the development of remote sensing and GIS has significantly advanced geomorphological research. Such data enable the extraction of morphometric parameters, surface modelling, and the production of various relief visualisations. However, greater data availability and higher spatial resolution do not automatically guarantee clearer interpretation. As data detail increases, so does the need for suitable visualisation methods capable of highlighting subtle variations in relief without reducing overall readability (Chiba and Hasi 2016, Kaneda and Chiba 2019). This is particularly important in the study of microrelief forms, where small elevation differences, slope breaks, and concave and convex surface features are often

crucial for precise quantitative analysis and final geomorphological interpretation. The term microrelief is here used to describe small-scale variations in the Earth's surface roughness which allows to better delineate different kind of forms at different scales and thus provide more precision in further analysis and interpretation.

Standard DEM visualisations, such as hillshade, contour lines and morphometric maps, have an important and established role in geomorphological analysis. However, their interpretative value is not the same for all types of relief or all analysis scales. Hillshade, for example, depends on illumination direction, so the visibility of individual forms depends on their orientation relative to the light source. This may obscure fine relief structures, while contour lines and morphometric indicators often do not depict subtle details clearly enough, especially on flattened or highly dissected surfaces (Chiba et al. 2008).

To improve the interpretation of such relief features, more advanced DEM visualisation methods have been developed, among which the Red Relief Image Map (RRIM) is particularly notable (Chiba et al. 2008). RRIM was developed to improve the representation of small and microrelief, with reduced dependence on illumination direction and clearer distinction between concave and convex parts of the surface. In Croatia, RRIM has not been frequently applied so far, and existing studies have mostly focused on larger study areas (Bočić et al. 2024, Maslač et al. 2024), while its use at the level of small and micro geomorphological forms has remained limited. The aim of this study is to assess the applicability of the RRIM method in the analysis of microrelief forms in selected morphogenetic relief types in Croatia and to compare it with standard DEM visualisations.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

Croatia is characterised by pronounced relief diversity resulting from the interaction of morphostructural, lithological, morphogenetic and hydrographic factors (Bognar 1999, Bognar et al. 2012). In this study, three areas with different morphogenetic characteristics were selected (Figure 1): the fluvial relief of the Zrmanja River, the glacial relief of Bilensko Mirovo, and the slope processes of Hrvatska Kostajnica. The Zrmanja River belongs to the group of tufa-forming streams of the Dinaric karst, with particularly significant tufa barriers developed in its middle course. The Hrvatska Kostajnica area is characterised by active slope processes, especially after the activation of a large landslide in March 2018 (Podolszki et al. 2022). Bilensko Mirovo on Northern Velebit is characterised by

glaciokarst relief. Glacial periods reshaped karstic forms during the Pleistocene glaciation. Particularly interesting is the terminal moraine between Bilensko Mirovo and Baričević dolac (Bognar et al. 1991, Velić et al. 2011).

2.2 Data, methods and analyses

The analysis was based on LiDAR-derived digital elevation model data with a spatial resolution of 1×1 m, provided by the State Geodetic Administration. Such resolution enables the representation of subtle relief variations and is suitable for analysing microrelief forms. For each selected location, comparative relief visualisations were produced and visually interpreted. Four visualisations were created for each locality: satellite imagery, hillshade, slope map, and RRIM. Hillshade and slope were used as standard comparative products because they are among the most commonly used visualisations in geomorphological analysis. Hillshade allows relief forms to be displayed, but its interpretative value depends strongly on the azimuth and elevation of the light source. A slope map shows the spatial distribution of steepness, but by itself does not clearly distinguish concave and convex parts of relief.

RRIM was produced as a composite visualisation based on slope and topographic openness. The method combines a slope layer and an index derived from positive and negative openness, whereby convex and concave surface parts are displayed simultaneously and independently of illumination direction (Chiba et al. 2008). Positive openness expresses surface convexity, while negative openness expresses concavity. In this study, RRIM was applied as the main tool for the visual interpretation of microrelief, while hillshade and slope were used as

comparative visualisations. The analysis was carried out in ArcGIS Pro software using a qualitative comparative approach based on the visual comparison of RRIM with hillshade and slope. The comparison focused on the clarity of landform representation, the visibility of their boundaries, the distinction between concave and convex surface parts, and the visibility of fine relief details.

3 Results

For all three analysed localities (Figure 1), comparative cartographic visualisations were produced, including satellite imagery, slope map, hillshade, and RRIM (Figure 2). Visual comparison revealed clear differences in their interpretative value. Satellite imagery proved useful for recognising land cover, vegetation, water surfaces and the approximate position of geomorphological forms, but did not provide a sufficiently clear insight into microrelief structure. Hillshade provided a clearer representation of general morphology and relief transitions, although its readability was partly limited by illumination direction. The slope map clearly emphasized steeper terrain parts and slope breaks, but was less suitable for understanding the spatial organization of forms. Compared to these visualizations, RRIM proved the most suitable for small and microrelief interpretation because it provides a clearer display of relief relationships while simultaneously emphasizing slope, the concave and the convex parts of the surface.

In the case of the Zrmanja River tufa barriers (Faivre et al. 2025), satellite imagery clearly shows the water surface, vegetation and the general position of the tuffa, but does not provide a sufficiently clear representation of their

Figure 1. Study area: 1-Hrvatska Kostajnica landslide; 2-Zrmanja tufa barriers; 3-Bilensko Mirovo glacial landforms.

microrelief structure. Hillshade improves the readability of the margins and crests of the tufa barriers, while the slope map clearly emphasizes steeper marginal zones and slope breaks. PRIM enables particularly clear delineation of tufa barriers as relief units and a distinct definition of their margins, orientations and fine morphological details. Consequently, surface area can be calculated, profiles can be done with best precision, what is all very important in geomorphological and paleoenvironmental reconstructions. Thus, RRIM revealed the most useful.

At the Kubarnovo brdo landslide in Hrvatska Kostajnica, differences between the visualizations are even more pronounced due to the complex morphology of the landslide body. Satellite imagery enables recognition of the general position of the landslide and the contrast between bare and vegetated parts of the slope, but does not show the detailed microrelief dissection. Hillshade clearly highlights the basic morphology of the landslide, especially the main scarp and lateral boundaries, while the slope map effectively emphasizes steeper parts and zones

of abrupt slope change. RRIM proved the most suitable because it shows the internal segmentation of the landslide body much more clearly, denivelations, and relationships between the concave and convex parts of the deformed slope, what could also help in differentiation of landslide types.

In Bilensko Mirovo, satellite imagery provides only a general overview of land-cover distribution, while glacial geomorphological forms are hardly recognizable. Hillshade enables recognition of the general terrain morphology, including elongated and rounded forms and marginal transitions related to the terminal moraine, while the slope map highlights steeper parts of the moraine margins and lateral transitions. RRIM proved particularly useful for displaying the overall microrelief dissection, as it enables clear identification of the terminal moraine, precise distinction of closed depressions like dolines, protrusions (gentle convex elevations) such as drumlins and eskers, as well as their mutual spatial relationships.

Figure 2. Comparison of satellite imagery and selected terrain visualisation models for the investigated sites: 1 – satellite image, 2 – hillshade, 3 – slope, 4 – RRIM; A – Hrvatska Kostajnica landslide, B – Zrmanja tufa barriers, C – Bilensko Mirovo, D – Bilensko Mirovo drumlin.

4 Discussion

The obtained results reveal the main advantages of RRIM emphasized by Chiba et al. (2008). Compared to standard hillshade and slope representation, RRIM provides a more uniform display of microrelief because it is not tied to a single illumination direction and simultaneously highlights slope and concave, convex surface relationships. In this study, this was evident at all analyzed localities, although not in the same way. As in earlier RRIM based studies, the comparison in this paper is primarily qualitative and based on the visual interpretability of the same terrain represented by different DEM visualizations. Therefore, RRIM is not treated here as universally superior, but rather as particularly effective in situations where subtle microtopographic relationships and concave/convex relief patterns are important for interpretation, also demonstrated by Chiba and Hasi (2016).

In the Zrmanja area, RRIM proved particularly valuable for the analysis of tufa barriers because it enables clearer highlighting of microtopographic forms than standard relief visualizations. This improved the interpretation of their morphology, margins, orientations and spatial organization. It is especially important that RRIM allows the recognition of those barriers or parts of them that are not sufficiently clear on other models, which is important for the identification of weakly preserved fossil tufa barriers. In Bilensko Mirovo, the results fit well with the studies of Bognar et al. (1991) who first provide detailed evidences on Pleistocene glaciations (different kind of moraines) and Velić et al. (2011), who provide further details on glacial landscape describing drumlins and eskers. The results of this study show that RRIM allows detailed extraction of these forms at the microrelief level. This applies especially to drumlins and eskers, while the terminal moraine is well distinguished as a unit on RRIM, although its boundaries are less unequivocal due to its dimensions and complexity. RRIM also clearly highlights smaller depressions that were interpreted as kettles by Velić et al (2011) but reveal today clear standard karst processes typical for dolines. RRIM does not replace geomorphological mapping but can serve as a very good basis for more precise geomorphological recognition, delimitation and quantification of forms described in previous research or analysis of new landforms. Similar conclusions can be applied to the

Kubarnovo brdo landslide in Hrvatska Kostajnica, where a multi-level analysis was carried out after landslide activation with the aim of developing a reliable landslide model and assessing the risk of reactivation (Podolszki et al. 2022). Although such studies include detailed geological, geophysical and remote sensing models, the results of this study show that RRIM can further improve surface geomorphological interpretation due to the clearer delineation of landslide margins, body and internal segmentation. It thus proves useful as a complementary tool in the initial phase of geomorphological interpretation and in better mapping of surface deformations, although by itself it cannot replace detailed field analyses.

5 Conclusions

The results of this study show that the main value of RRIM lies in its ability to improve the microgeomorphological readability of relief forms in different morphogenetic contexts, environments and scales. Compared with standard DEM visualizations, RRIM enabled a clearer display of relief relationships at all analyzed locations, although the nature of its advantage varied depending on the geomorphological context. In Zrmanja, it proved particularly useful for better interpretation of tufa barriers, their margins, orientations and spatial organization, while also facilitating the identification of weakly distinguishable features, including eroded fossil tufa barriers. In Hrvatska Kostajnica, it enabled a better understanding of the internal dissection of the landslide body and complete surface deformations, while in Bilensko Mirovo it contributed to a clearer extraction of glacial landforms, especially the terminal moraine, drumlins and eskers. At the same time, RRIM may be less effective for larger and morphologically simpler landforms, or in cases where broader terrain context, absolute elevation, or slope direction are more important than subtle microrelief expression. The obtained results indicate that RRIM does not replace existing geomorphological approaches, but effectively complements them, especially in the phase of detailed mapping of subtle relief structures and their quantitative analysis.

6 References

- Bočić, N., Pahernik, M., Redovniković, L., Buzjak, N., 2024. Making a geomorphological map in karst area based on high resolution DEM: experiences from the Plitvice Lakes National Park (Croatia). In: Kogovšek, B., Švara, A., Gabrovšek, F. et al. (Eds.), 31st International Karstological School "Classical karst", Data acquisition and analysis in karst systems, Abstracts & guide book. ZRC SAZU, Karst Research Institute, Postojna, pp. 59-60.
- Bognar, A., 1999. Geomorfološka regionalizacija Hrvatske. *Acta Geographica Croatica*, 34(1), 7-26.
- Bognar, A., Faivre, S., Buzjak, N., Pahernik, M., Bočić, N., 2012. Recent landform evolution in the Dinaric and Pannonian regions of Croatia. In: Loczy, D., Stankoviansky, M., Kotarba, A. (Eds.), *Recent Landform Evolution, The Carpatho-Balkan-Dinaric Region*. Springer Verlag, pp. 313-344.
- Bognar, A., Faivre, S., Pavelić, J., 1991. Tragovi oledbe na Sjevernom Velebitu. *Geografski glasnik* 53, 27-39.
- Chiba, T., Hasi, B., 2016. Ground surface visualization using red relief image map for a variety of map scales. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 41, 393-397.
- Chiba, T., Kaneta, S.I., Suzuki, Y., 2008. Red relief image map: new visualization method for three dimensional data. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* 37 (B2), 1071-1076.
- Faivre, S., Veverec, I., Barešić, J., Krajcar Bronić, I., Sironić, A., Drysdale, R.N., 2025. Morphogenesis of tufa barriers in Zrmanja river valley (External Dinarides, Croatia). In: Fuerst-Bjeliš, B. (Ed.), *Geography in its complexity*.

- International conference in honour of the work of Prof. Veljko Rogić (1925-2017) on the occasion of the 100th anniversary of his birth, Krasno - Mt. Velebit, Croatia, September 18-19, 2025. University of Zagreb, Faculty of Science, Department of Geography; Croatian Geographical Society, Zagreb, 63-64.
- Hengl, T. and Reuter, H.I. eds., 2008. *Geomorphometry: concepts, software, applications* (Vol. 33). Newnes.
- Kaneda, H. and Chiba, T., 2019. Stereopaired morphometric protection index red relief image maps (Stereo MPI-RRIMs): Effective visualization of high-resolution digital elevation models for interpreting and mapping small tectonic geomorphic features. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 109(1), pp.99-109.
- Maslač Soldo, J., Kordić, B., Rupnik, P.J., Matoš, B., 2024. Processing LiDAR data for geomorphological mapping of active faults: A case study of Sveta Nedelja Fault (Žumberak Mt.). In: 1st International Conference of Environmental Remote Sensing and GIS (ICERS). University of Zagreb, Faculty of Geodesy, pp. 39-42.
- Podolszki, L., Kosović, I., Novosel, T., Kurečić, T., 2021. Multi-level sensing technologies in landslide research—Hrvatska Kostajnica case study, Croatia. *Sensors* 22 (1), 177.
- Velić, J., Velić, I., Kljajo, D., 2011. Sedimentary bodies, forms and occurrences in the Tudorevo and Mirovo glacial deposits of northern Velebit (Croatia). *Geologia Croatica* 64 (1), 1-16.